

The FAIR Principles

The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship are a set of minimal guiding principles and practices for enabling curation, maintenance, and long-term preservation of data to improve the digital infrastructure that supports the (re)use of scholarly data. They describe an aspirational philosophy for managing digital research objects (e.g., data sets, code, workflows, visualizations, etc.).

↔ “Distinct from peer initiatives that focus on the human scholar, the **FAIR Principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines** to automatically find and use the data, **in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals.**”

Wilkinson et al. 2016, emphasis added.

Findible **A**ccessible **I**nteroperable **R**eusable

The FAIR Principles seek to ensure the discoverability and reusability of digital research objects by mandating they be:

Findable:

Digital resources should be:

- easy to find for machines and humans alike
- assigned a unique, persistent, and resolvable identifier
- described with rich metadata that are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible:

Identifiers make metadata retrievable by using a standardized and explicit communications protocol that is:

- open for both machines and humans
- cost free
- universally implementable.

This includes well-defined authorization mechanisms for access to protected data.

Interoperable:

Data objects and metadata represent knowledge using a language that is:

- formalized
- accessible
- shared
- broadly applicable.

Clear semantics for each resource - whether an object or a service - is a prerequisite.

Reusable:

Digital objects are shared or published with a clear and as-open-as-possible license.

A machine decides if an object:

- should be reused,
- can be reused,
- under what conditions,
- to whose credit.

This ensures rightful provenance and complies with community standards for describing them sufficiently for computer and human use.

 Find scholarly resources on the FAIR Principles in the EOSC SOA Zotero Library.

